

Feed additives for methane mitigation: Assessment of feed additives as a strategy to mitigate enteric methane from ruminants—Accounting; How to quantify the mitigating potential of using antimethanogenic feed additives

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in our understanding of methanogenesis have led to the development of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) that can reduce enteric methane (CH₄) emissions to varying extents, via direct targeting of methanogens, alternative electron acceptors, or altering the rumen environment. Here we examine current and new approaches used for the accounting (i.e., quantification) of enteric CH₄ abatement by the use of AMFA in the livestock sector from the individual animal to the global scale. Along with this process, recommendations are provided on how to account for the mitigation potential at the animal level, as well as in farm-scale models, emissions trading schemes, life cycle assessment, and carbon (C) footprinting tools, and in regional and national inventories. In addition, an assessment of uncertainties and potential trade-offs and off-setting with the use of AMFA (i.e., efficacy vs. effectiveness, upstream and downstream emissions) is provided. The accounting of on-farm enteric CH₄ emissions and benefits from the use of AMFA starts with the ruminant animal (with estimates obtained from a range of approaches, from simple empirical emission factors or equations to complex process-based models) and goes all the way to

national and supranational accounting. The choice of methodologies and levels of complexity to account for mitigation of enteric CH₄ (or total GHG) emissions in livestock systems must be tailored to the scale of analysis aimed, the availability of input data to represent contextualized conditions, and the accounting objectives (e.g., academic exercise vs. producer's GHG certification vs. national GHG inventory). The accounting of enteric CH₄ mitigating effects needs to consider the AMFA delivery methods and synergies and trade-offs of GHG emissions at levels before and beyond (upstream and downstream) the animal to fully assess the impact of AMFA use. At large, the accounting of methane abatement by feed additives remains to be fully assessed beyond experimental results (efficacy) to address pragmatism (effectiveness), potential for adoption, and societal acceptance.

Key words: life cycle assessment, carbon footprint, emission trading schemes, modeling, greenhouse gases

INTRODUCTION

There is increasing recognition that pressing action must take place to avoid the risks and effects of climate change. In this process, individuals, organizations, and governments are introducing measures to reduce GHG emissions, and we need to be able to comprehensively quantify GHG emissions abatement. Enteric methane (CH₄) emissions from livestock systems mainly originate from microbial fermentation and methanogenesis occurring in the forestomach of ruminants. Recent advances in

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our understanding of methanogenesis have led to the development of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) that can reduce enteric CH₄ emissions to varying extents, via direct targeting of methanogens, alternative electron acceptors, or altering the rumen environment (Honan et al., 2022; Belanche et al., 2025; Durmic et al., 2025).

Recent global reports on ruminant agriculture and climate change have included the co-benefits, risks, and implementation opportunities and barriers (IPCC, 2022), environmental impact (FAO, 2020; Blonk et al., 2021), efficacy (Hegarty et al., 2021; Honan et al., 2022; FAO, 2023), and accrediting methodology (e.g., VERRA Verified Carbon Standard; VERRA, 2021) of AMFA and their enteric CH₄ abatement potential. The IPCC (2022) report emphasizes the robust evidence and prominent level of consensus of promising AMFA as effective near-term measures for significant enteric CH₄ mitigation. Out of 10 AMFA or additive groups assessed by Hegarty et al. (2021), 2 of them, 3-nitrooxypropanol (3-NOP) and halogen-methane containing dried *Asparagopsis* sp. (red algae), consistently achieved >20% enteric CH₄ abatement, followed by dietary nitrate (>10%), with other AMFA or additive groups generally expected to achieve <10% abatement. However, risks, concerns, and uncertainties of using AMFA have been raised, such as potential effects on palatability, toxicity, and animal welfare; feeding and administration constraints; legal requirements to authorize their use (Tricarico et al., 2025); and the need for supply chains at scale and good manufacturing practice. In addition, there is an increasing need for adequate accounting of these abatement strategies. This includes the benefits of reducing enteric CH₄ (IPCC, 2022), as well as the potential trade-offs and synergies in relation to CH₄ emissions from other processes. For example, if AMFA supplementation leads to reduced feed digestibility, it could potentially result in increased CH₄ emissions from manure emissions. It is also important to consider other sources of GHG, non-GHG nitrogen emissions, upstream emissions of AMFA, and the overall performance of ruminants.

This paper examines current and new approaches used for the accounting of enteric CH₄ abatement by the use of AMFA in the livestock sector from the individual animal to the global scale. Recommendations (illustrated in Figure 1) are provided on the methods to account in farm-scale models, emissions trading schemes (ETS), life cycle assessment (LCA; often referred as carbon footprint when measuring the GHG impact of a product through every phase of its life) and in regional and national inventories. The term “accounting” herein refers mostly to the quantification of enteric CH₄ abatement at different scales, and to a lesser extent, to the quantification of uncertainties and potential trade-offs or off-setting with AMFA use (i.e., efficacy vs. effectiveness, other un-

certainties affecting efficacy, upstream and downstream emissions).

ACCOUNTING AT DIFFERENT SCALES

The accounting of the efficacy of AMFA to mitigate enteric CH₄ emissions in ruminant livestock systems involves the use of generic estimates, empirical equations, or other modeling approaches (Dijkstra et al., 2025) implemented in tools that may be applied at different scales (animal, herd, farm, regional, and national; Hristov et al., 2018; Tedeschi et al., 2022). The intervention with AMFA may involve various compounds with different modes of action (Belanche et al., 2025) such as lipids, ionophores, phytochemicals, essential oils, algae, electron acceptors (i.e., nitrate and sulfate), and 3-NOP or other methanogen inhibiting agents such as bromoform (Almeida et al., 2021; Honan et al., 2022). Feed additives can reduce enteric CH₄ emission directly, mainly via reduced CH₄ production (grams per day per cow), with an effect on emissions yield (grams per kilogram of DMI) and intensity (grams per kilogram of animal product; e.g., milk or BW gain), indirectly by improving animal performance (i.e., by altering the amounts of rumen fermented OM), or both. Positive effects on animal performance will incentivize the use of AMFA when there is no direct reward for their use to reduce CH₄ emissions (Dijkstra et al., 2025), but this is beyond the scope of this paper.

The accounting of CH₄ emissions abatement at any scale (from animal and farm-scale accounting to national inventory) requires critical background data such as animal characteristics, dosage, and characteristics of the AMFA and the feed used as a means of delivery, and mitigation efficacy and effectiveness within the farming system. Such information should be available, and well-documented evidence is required to be considered in any accounting process. Enteric CH₄ prediction models vary in level of detail and complexity represented, ranging from relatively simple empirical (or statistical) models to more detailed and comprehensive process-based mechanistic models that represent the underlying biological processes leading to enteric CH₄ emissions (Kebreab et al., 2016; Dijkstra et al., 2025). Additionally, C footprint and LCA methodology may be used to provide a more holistic view of the environmental impact (Cowie et al., 2012) including on-farm and off-farm emissions, and upstream and downstream effects. Hence, the scale of assessment, the methodology used for the accounting of CH₄ emissions (Hristov et al., 2025), and the volume and quality of data collected are interrelated factors. When the assessment is conducted at a smaller scale (i.e., animal, groups of animals, herd, or farm), data required as input of mechanistic models tend to be collected more frequently (often daily or even including diurnal aspects)

ACCOUNTING SYSTEMS TO QUANTIFY CH₄ AND GHG EMISSIONS AND MITIGATION FROM LIVESTOCK

	For any mitigation measure	Specific for accounting of enteric CH ₄ abatement by AMFA		
		Approaches	Uncertainties	Consider
General	Well-documented and verified methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the variables that impact efficacy and effectiveness of AMFA AMFA benefits = f(diet, animal type, AMFA mode of action, AMFA dosage, AMFA delivery method, AMFA combinations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Until large empirical database becomes available that includes all combinations of AMFA at various dosages, mechanistic modelling is preferable Mechanistic modeling may help reduce uncertainties and improve tools for farm GHG assessment, C accounting, and GHG inventory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synergies/trade-offs on GHG and other emissions Upstream/downstream emissions Legislation/Regulations
Animal				
Farm				
LCA	Report the shortcomings of methodology (e.g., approach too generic, not fully reflecting site conditions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All impact categories for synergies/trade-offs Off-farm AMFA emissions? Careful to extrapolate AMFA results at other levels Report limitations 		
Country		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear documentation linked to AMFA is recommended as specified in IPCC (2019) Capturing combined AMFA efficacy and effectiveness: experimental work and models 		
ETS	Methodologies tailored on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> scale of analysis availability of input data specific objectives and requirements of ETS 			

Figure 1. Summary of recommendations on how to account for enteric methane (CH₄) abatement (general and focusing on antimethanogenic feed additive [AMFA] use) and the associated uncertainties and other non-CH₄ emissions at the animal, farm, life cycle assessment (LCA), and countrywide scales, as well as in emissions trading schemes (ETS). EF = emission factor; f = function of. Created by A. del Prado and Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

Figure 2. Animal, farm, and life cycle assessment (LCA) boundaries for the accounting of enteric methane (CH_4) emissions. Adapted from Cowie et al.(2012) by Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

compared with larger scales (region, country, continent). In general, the more detailed the data required and equations or models applied, the greater the reliability of national accounting as a whole (van Lingen et al., 2019). Before delving into a detailed discussion of the various aspects of accounting for enteric CH_4 emissions in AMFA, this section provides a general overview of the methods used at the animal, farm, and broader scales for livestock GHG quantification.

Animal

The accounting of on-farm enteric CH_4 emissions and benefits from the use of AMFA starts with the ruminant animal, and estimates are obtained using a range of methods, from simple empirical emission factors or equations to complex process-based models (Figure 2). At the animal scale, relatively simple estimates of enteric CH_4 emissions are often obtained from prediction equations including DMI, either alone or in combination with the chemical composition of diet constituents (e.g., fiber content; Niu et al., 2018). Accounting can gain complexity (and often accuracy) by adding certain characteristics of the animal, such as BW and animal product (milk, meat, or fiber; Kebreab et al., 2016; Dijkstra et al., 2025). Emissions can also be estimated according to a set of defined data, with estimates of daily DMI per animal,

derived from tabulated energy requirements or feeding standards (often based on BW, maintenance needs, tissue growth, milk production, pregnancy, and activity) divided by the energy concentration of the feed (IPCC, 2019). The digestible energy (DE) value of a feed can be estimated from OM digestibility, or from feed chemical composition and digestibility coefficients in the literature. Feed DE can also be estimated by using a combination of chemical composition data and prediction equations. Some more advanced models predict DE and OM and nitrogen (N) digestibility mechanistically (Beukes et al., 2011; Bannink et al., 2018).

An essential step for the prediction of a diet-specific enteric CH_4 emission is the calculation of a CH_4 conversion factor expressing a percent of feed gross energy intake (GEI) converted to CH_4 (often referred as methane conversion factor, Y_m) or a CH_4 yield (CH_4 produced per unit of feed intake). Methane emission values are obtained by either multiplying DMI or GEI by a CH_4 yield or a fixed CH_4 conversion factor, for example, Y_m (percentage of feed gross energy converted to CH_4) with values specified in IPCC (2019), respectively. Both Y_m and CH_4 yield values should be obtained locally (most likely from respiration chambers) or through an equation that might include dietary ingredients, chemical composition parameters, digestibility parameters, and animal characteristics. Process-based mechanistic models with

representation of rumen fermentation and gastrointestinal digestion may be used to predict Y_m values (Bannink et al., 2011; Huhtanen et al., 2015; Dijkstra et al., 2025).

Farm

The farm represents the land scale at which management decisions on livestock production are made (Figure 2). Most emissions and variability within the life cycle of agricultural products often occur within the farming system, that is, within the farm gate and not during the rest of the life cycle of livestock production (Oenema et al., 2003). This is of particular relevance in the case of enteric CH_4 , which is essentially the result of feed quality, intake within a given animal category, and, in the context of this work, the use of compounds that modulate rumen fermentation. Therefore, farm-level models and the accurate estimation of enteric CH_4 emissions play a pivotal role in addressing the mitigation of GHG emissions in livestock agriculture. On-farm GHG models have been developed and used by the scientific community, environmental authorities, farm consultants, and farmers for the accounting of enteric CH_4 emissions (see examples of farm models referenced in the following paragraph). Those models serve several crucial functions, including integral assessment of all GHG sources and raising awareness. They will also have to be used to identify, develop, and promote efficacy of alternative AMFA and it is therefore important to pinpoint knowledge gaps, as well as being able to scale up information for policy development. Measurements on AMFA efficacy are normally performed with individual animals as experimental units (Hristov et al., 2025) comprising different animal categories for regulatory purposes (Tricarico et al., 2025). This basis may differ from the way an individual animal or animal cohorts are represented in farm-scale approaches where, for operational purposes, different simplifications and assumptions are made. In this case, AMFA and animal cohort specifications and assumptions need to be well-documented.

At the farm scale, on-farm GHG models offer a broader diversity of scope, modeling approach, and scale (i.e., from the rumen to the site, the landscape, and the whole farm; Schils et al., 2007; Crosson et al., 2011; Colomb et al., 2012; del Prado et al., 2013; Kebreab et al., 2016; Vibart et al., 2021). Even though models are usually labeled as empirical or mechanistic, it is common to find a combination of both approaches within a single model, each applied to different components (Dijkstra et al., 2025). In general, farm-scale models tend to follow hybrid or empirical approaches to integrate soil, crop and pasture, and livestock components into a farm framework (Schils et al., 2012). This type of integrated approach al-

lows for an overall estimate of direct as well as indirect GHG and N emissions including their trade-offs and synergies, and it allows comparisons between different production systems, between different production conditions, or both (Schils et al., 2007; del Prado et al., 2013; Ouatahar et al., 2021). When evaluating GHG mitigation strategies from livestock systems, models that are able to capture internal feedbacks and loops of C and N between farm components are preferred (del Prado et al., 2013) because mitigation measures that benefit one farm component (e.g., enteric CH_4 fermentation) may affect C and N flows in other components, for example, CH_4 emissions at the manure-management level (del Prado et al., 2013). Moreover, modeling approaches must be capable of simulating the interactions between combined mitigation strategies that may not necessarily be additive (del Prado et al., 2010; Owens et al., 2020). Farm models can distinguish how much of the mitigation comes from each strategy through scenario testing. First a baseline scenario is simulated and subsequently, simulations with farm scenarios where changes are introduced singly and in a stepwise process are carried out. Each step would introduce a new different change in strategy (e.g., involving feed management). The changes, acting singly or in combination, are then evaluated on farms. In addition to the representation of the AMFA CH_4 mitigating effect, focus is needed on the effect of AMFA on feed digestibility, excretion, and animal performance (Belanche et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025) and how to quantify these effects (Dijkstra et al., 2025).

Recommendations

- Precisely define the aims of any farm-scale modeling effort and what aspects and details that are relevant at the animal and subanimal scale have and have not been covered (Dijkstra et al., 2025). The representativeness of integrated models often depends on their ability to accurately depict a specific farm within a particular region (i.e., the model captures the intricacies of local soil, climate, farm management, and animal policy data). This highlights the limitation of a “one-size-fits-all” model or model assumptions for all farms. Often, the lack of specificity and logicity in the representation of the underlying processes that lead to GHG and N emissions attempt against the integrating and overarching approach of modeling at the whole-farm scale because some parts are too simplified and represented by empirical approaches (Ouatahar et al., 2021).
- Consider estimating CH_4 and nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions from manure management, land applica-

tion, and feces and urine deposition (resulting from feed intake and digestibility), as well as manure treatment when evaluating dietary effects. These emissions are influenced not only by diet characteristics but also by biotic and abiotic factors.

- Report the available data to support model evaluation or validation. Generally, these data will be limited to few farm components.

Life Cycle Assessment

Although farm-level GHG emissions balance simulation models fall within the category of systems analysis models and, thus, attempt to explicitly represent the flows and transformation of C and N, also other approaches are mainly emission factor-based and center around LCA (Crosson et al., 2011; del Prado et al., 2013). Life cycle assessment is generally accepted as a holistic method or framework to evaluate the environmental impact, such as climate change or C footprint as one of the indicators, during the entire life cycle of a product and relates it to a functional unit expressed in quantitative terms (Guinée et al., 2002; de Vries and de Boer, 2010; Figure 2). The LCA analysis requires specific data from the animal and farm boundaries to achieve a more detailed and specific assessment (Figure 2). There are 2 main types: attributional LCA (**aLCA**), which assesses the global impact share of a product's life cycle, and consequential LCA (**cLCA**), which evaluates the consequential impact of a decision (Schaubroeck, 2023). The C footprint is the sum of GHG emissions associated with a product or activity, expressed in units of carbon dioxide equivalents (**CO₂-eq**; Flachowsky and Kamphues, 2012). The use of LCA to quantify the environmental impact of different products has increased in recent years and is often driven by demands for accountability from customers, stakeholders, and government regulators (Beauchemin and McGeough, 2013). The International Standards Organization (**ISO**) offers guidelines and established benchmarks for the calculation and communication of the environmental impact of food products.

Country

Signatory countries to the Paris Agreement need to report annually their national emission GHG inventory to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Simultaneously, climate action plans to lower GHG emissions through nationally determined contributions (**NDC**), have shown that about 36% of countries included livestock and grassland mitigation interventions in their most recent NDC (Crumpler et al., 2021). At the national inventory scale, the accounting of enteric CH₄

emissions can be either simple generic and easily accessible, be locally obtained, or be driven by process-based mechanistic models. The IPCC Guidelines explain the approach of the 3 tiers of complexity in the estimation of enteric CH₄ emissions from ruminant livestock systems (IPCC, 2006, 2019). The choice of which approach each country uses for their inventory is based on data availability, research or scientific resources, and mechanistic models adapted for the conditions. The less that is known about livestock and feed characteristics, the more uncertain the inventory is likely to be (Hristov et al., 2018). In countries where an extensive database exists, mostly a Tier 2 or adapted Tier 2 approach is followed, whereas in countries with a detailed and extensive scientific knowledge base on digestive and enteric fermentative processes, a Tier 3 approach may be used. With each tier, aiming to represent efficacy of a AMFA linkage must be made with modeling results at the animal scale (Dijkstra et al., 2025).

The latest refinement to the IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019) proposes different Y_m values to those proposed by IPCC (2006) for cattle and buffalo (6.5% of GEI in IPCC 2006) linked to annual milk production levels (dairy animals) and to feed quantity and quality. For example, the lowest Y_m value (5.7% of GEI) is associated with high producing dairy cattle that are fed diets with >70% digestibility and that have a percentage of NDF in DMI <35%, whereas the highest Y_m value (7% of GEI) must be chosen for nondairy cattle that graze on low-quality forage diets.

The Tier 2 methods can use the same approach as Tier 1 but with country- or region-specific energy requirement models to calculate emission factors (i.e., altering Y_m values; Lassey, 2007; Hellwing et al., 2016; Colombini et al., 2023). Tier 2 methods allow for a higher spatial and temporal resolution and data livestock category disaggregation (i.e., sex, age, management, or season; Kouazounde et al., 2015; Ibidhi et al., 2021; Ndung'u et al., 2023). Countries often lack sufficient data related to livestock to move beyond Tier 1. Most GHG inventories use the IPCC Tier 1 approach, which only reflects changes in livestock numbers. Monitoring changes in management and productivity necessitates using a Tier 2 approach. The lack of activity data and incomplete or poor-quality data are commonly seen as obstacles to implementing the Tier 2 approach. A recent review revealed that out of 140 low- and middle-income countries (**LMIC**), just 92 have included livestock-related emissions in their NDC (FAO and GRA, 2020).

Tier 3 methods are of a higher order of detail and resolution, and tailored to assess at the subnational or regional scale, and may, but do not necessarily have to, involve process-based modeling that considers DMI, diet

chemical composition, and feed degradation and fermentation characteristics to predict enteric CH₄ emissions (Vibart et al., 2021). Models used in Tier 3 represent rumen fermentation mechanisms, capturing a greater portion of the variability from nutritional and animal factors, with enhanced precision when using local data from experiments and validated calculation methods (Bannink et al., 2011; Kebreab et al., 2016). However, the necessary data are not typically gathered and promptly available and must be grounded in prior *in situ* rumen incubation studies and national diet component statistics (Bannink et al., 2011). Therefore, in countries where no such data are available, a Tier 1 approach is commonly followed, mostly in LMIC.

Emissions Trading Schemes

To assist in meeting their emissions-abatement commitments, countries are increasingly developing regional and national ETS, a tool designed for the purpose of meeting domestic and international climate change targets. These market-based schemes aim to create economic incentives for emissions reduction from effective practices implemented at the least overall cost possible (Cowie et al., 2012). The Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative (cap and reduce emissions from the power sector) and the Western Climate Initiative (collaborative development and implementation of ETS programs) are examples of regional schemes in the United States. Likewise, the European ETS (operates on cap-and-trade principles), Australia's Carbon Farming Initiative (a voluntary carbon offsets scheme) and the New Zealand ETS (all sectors of New Zealand's economy) are examples of national and supranational schemes that have different scopes and purposes. Approved methodologies for GHG accounting are essential to the success of these schemes (Cowie et al., 2012). But to our knowledge, very few of these schemes include livestock agriculture in their accounting systems. One of the few livestock agriculture schemes includes incorporating nitrates in Australian beef cattle. The methodology sets the rules for the emissions abatement achieved by replacing urea lick blocks with nitrate lick blocks used in pasture-based beef cattle systems, with accreditation managed by the Australian Carbon Credit Unit scheme (Australian Government, 2023).

If AMFA are to be incorporated as an abatement strategy in ETS and the point of obligation is set at the farmer level, then the accounting approach in these agricultural schemes would be similar to that used for farm-scale accounting (i.e., being able to account at the animal scale). But if the point of obligation is set at the (animal product) processing level, then the accounting approach would most likely be similar to that used for regional or national inventory accounting.

APPROACHES TO THE ACCOUNTING OF ENTERIC METHANE ABATEMENT BY AMFA

Animal, Farm, National, and Supranational Scales

During the past 60 years, a wide range of AMFA have been tested and experimentally included in diets of dairy cows (de Oндarza et al., 2023; Figure 3A). The type of diet, AMFA delivery (in every mouthful of a TMR vs. pulse-fed with supplements), and production system (i.e., forage-to-concentrate ratio, fiber, soluble sugars, starch, and protein content) will determine not only the effectiveness of the AMFA but also the suitability for such feeding regimen (Dijkstra et al., 2018). Kebreab et al. (2023) in a recent metanalysis reported that increases in NDF and crude fat concentrations above the average in the database reduced effectiveness of 3-NOP at mitigating CH₄ production and yield, whereas increases in starch content enhanced 3-NOP effectiveness in mitigating CH₄ yield. In diets that are deficient in N, the diversion of electron flows by nitrates into alternative pathways of H₂ use in the rumen (i.e., a reduction to ammonia) can provide both an effective CH₄ mitigation alternative and a substrate for anabolism and supply of fermentable N from enhanced microbial protein synthesis (Dijkstra et al., 1998; van Zijderveld et al., 2010). Although it has been argued that AMFA may be less effective in ruminants fed diets that result in less CH₄ (e.g., diets high in grains), dietary factors did not come forward in a meta-analysis of observed variation in the CH₄ mitigating effect of added nitrate (Dijkstra et al., 2025). To note, external electron acceptors may also produce toxic end compounds (i.e., sulfides, nitrates/nitrites) affecting animal performance (Latham et al., 2016).

To accelerate the development of effective CH₄ mitigation technologies, there is a pressing need to comprehend the changes brought in the rumen by the use of AMFA and their effect on CH₄ formation (Belanche et al., 2025). When evaluating the absolute reduction in GHG emissions from the use of a specific AMFA, it is crucial to account for the potential reduction in CH₄ yield (g CH₄/kg of DMI), a metric that links both enteric CH₄ emissions and intake. A further refinement to this metric is to express CH₄ yield in terms of CH₄ production per unit of digested OM (DOM; g CH₄/kg of DOM intake) because it provides a finer description of feed being fermented and contributing to the fermentation profile (Beauchemin et al., 2022).

With an assessment at the farm scale, a CH₄ mitigating effect could be represented by a default value of correction (Tier 1; see previous section). For example, assuming the same amounts of feed are offered to ruminants (i.e., diets with and without AMFA), it would be feasible to apply default values around 30% and 10% for enteric

Figure 3. Global data set of enteric methane (CH_4) mitigation experiments, including the use of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA), in lactating dairy cows, conducted between 1963 and 2022 (adapted from de Ondarza et al., 2023). (A) Distribution of studies involving animals supplemented with the main AMFA categorized by their dietary composition (% of forage). (B) Methane yield ($\text{g CH}_4/\text{kg}$ of DMI) from animals that received AMFA compared with the control group. The bold line in the middle of each box plot represents the median. The box itself represents the interquartile range, spanning from the 25th percentile (bottom of the box) to the 75th percentile (top of the box). Whiskers represent a certain range beyond the IQR. The violin plot gives a mirrored density distribution for each group, showing the full distribution shape and adding depth to the raincloud plot, which combines summary statistics (box plot) with data distribution (violin plot and individual points). The point and line in the center of each cloud represents its mean and SE. The rain represents individual data points. (C) Methane emissions intensities ($\text{g CH}_4/\text{kg}$ of milk) for AMFA that show significant differences in CH_4 yield and their relationship with individual milk production (kg of milk per head [hd] per day). 3-NOP = 3-nitrooxypropanol; E. Acceptor = electron acceptor; Reg. = regression. Created by F. Bilotto and Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

CH₄ yield reduction (per kilogram of DMI) in dairy systems using 3-NOP and lipids, respectively (Figure 3B). Although such default values of CH₄ reduction by AMFA are easy to implement in accounting, the assumption inherently made is that conditions in practice match the experimental conditions these values were derived from (Dijkstra et al., 2025). Because this is often not the case, it is expected that this Tier 1 level of accounting for CH₄ reduction will be associated with a significant degree of uncertainty (see the “Uncertainties” section). It needs to be noted that a generic estimate only applies to the same average dosing and conditions of the empirical data used to derive these estimates. In any case, the number of experimental trials conducted in farm conditions where CH₄ measurement methods do not interrupt their daily behavior and routine (Hristov et al., 2025) and conducted over longer periods of time (more than 12 to 14 wk to a whole year) is expanding (van Gastelen et al., 2024). This increases the confidence when translating mitigation values obtained experimentally into practical farming.

As we move from Tier 1 to Tier 2 and Tier 3 approaches, observed variation needs to be captured with more detail and finer resolution. In this context, a more in-depth examination of nutritional data is imperative, given the diversity among livestock systems. Feed intake, feed digestibility, and CH₄ emissions are positively correlated with animal and herd size, growth rate, activity, and production level, and these differ between animal types and feed management practices (Hristov et al., 2018). Figure 3C portrays a decreasing trend in CH₄ mitigation potential of AMFA as the production level, energy, and protein content of the diet increase. Higher feed quality and digestibility, often associated with a reduction in retention time in the rumen due to faster passage rates leading to lower CH₄ yields (Beauchemin et al., 2022), sometimes result in relatively modest reductions in emissions when AMFA are introduced. However, the opposite (i.e., significant reductions in enteric CH₄ from cows fed highly digestible diets) has also been shown, as demonstrated for 3-NOP in a year-long study (van Gastelen et al., 2024), and no such indications were seen for nitrate (Feng et al., 2020).

Recommendations

- Incrementally improving the resolution of variables that influence the efficacy of AMFA in an emissions inventory is essential. This will result in a more precise and accurate assessment of the effects of AMFA in specific types of nutritional management, as well as in animal and farm systems.
- The simplest way to incorporate the effect of AMFA in GHG accounting systems is by using the default unit of percent reduction of CH₄ per amount of

ingested feed by the animal (e.g., per kilogram of DMI). This percentage must take into account the basic interactions between feed intake and the type of diet, as well as the mode of action, delivery method, and effective dosage of the AMFA.

- More complex approaches can improve the estimates of enteric CH₄ reduction currently available from meta-analyses. These approaches can also attribute expectations for various combinations of AMFA and dietary strategies.

At the farm scale, del Prado et al. (2010) simulated the inclusion of lipid-based additives (in isolation and in combination) as one of several strategies to improve dairy farm sustainability in the United Kingdom using the whole-farm model SIMS_{DAIRY} (del Prado et al., 2011). For enteric CH₄, the approach was based on an empirical equation that included animal DMI and the degree of unsaturation of the fatty acids in the diet with CH₄ output expressed per kilogram of DMI (Giger-Reverdin et al., 2003). Other meta-analyses have not established a clear effect of type of fatty acid on CH₄ abatement (e.g., Grainger and Beauchemin, 2011). Due to variation in the type of diets, AMFA mode of action, and feeding management (confinement feeding vs. a sole or supplemented grazing system), the extent to which CH₄ abatement is effective is harder to capture, and consequently also empirical equations can still be poor predictors of GHG emissions in a specific farm (Vibart et al., 2021).

Recommendations

- Include sufficient detail on livestock and feeding conditions, such as comparing barn and pasture conditions.
- Provide a comprehensive assessment of synergies and trade-offs within the farming operation (del Prado et al., 2013).
- Include effects on level of feed intake and animal performance, allowance of metabolizable energy (e.g., Belanche et al., 2025; van Gastelen et al., 2024), feed digestibility, excretion of urine and feces, as well as manure capture and storage.

To our knowledge, GHG emission inventories at the national scale are yet to account for the use of AMFA. Other types of additives (e.g., to improve the digestibility of specific nutrients, particularly proteins) directly affecting feed utilization and animal performance may have been automatically incorporated due to the highly empirical nature of the activity data and nutritional requirements. For example, the inclusion and accounting of new enzymes and synthetic amino acids in Spanish pig diets in the 2007 to 2010 period resulted in a reduc-

tion in protein intake and a notable decrease in N excretion and subsequent manure N₂O emissions (MAPA, 2024). Most countries have adopted hybrid Tier 1/Tier 2 approaches to account for enteric CH₄ emissions from ruminant systems. In the latest refinement of IPCC Guidelines (IPCC, 2019) there is explicit mention of the basics of how to best reflect the effect of AMFA in an inventory compilation at Tier 2 or Tier 3 (largely by altering Y_m), but no accounting is specified for mitigation practices using AMFA. The need for strong scientific evidence behind thorough peer-reviewed articles, including a description of the technology, its efficacy, and validation under field conditions, was highlighted. Additionally, paraphrasing: “It is good practice that the inventory be accompanied by evidence of the uptake of the technology in agricultural practice and apply it only to emissions by those livestock where uptake can be validated.” Only theoretically, several studies analyzed the effect of including AMFA at the national scale. For example, Hörtenhuber et al. (2023) considered a theoretical reduction by 5% (phytogenic feed), 10% (mixture phytogenic feed + 3-NOP), and 20% (3-NOP) of enteric CH₄ emission in Austrian cattle. Almeida et al. (2023) simulated the separate inclusion of 2 AMFA commercially available (phytochemicals and nitrate) and 2 novel AMFA in the process of entering the market (bromoform-containing *Asparagopsis* sp. and 3-NOP) in New South Wales using the results from a previously published meta-analysis on the potential abatement of each of these additives (Almeida et al., 2021). Applying results from such meta-analysis is complicated due to a knowledge gap on what to expect from a combined use of different AMFA (Hristov et al., 2025).

The use of alternative global warming potential (GWP) metrics, such as GWP* (Cain et al., 2019), may be considered when accounting for enteric CH₄ emissions abatement. The GWP100 climate metric is commonly used to express non-CO₂ GHG emissions as CO₂-eq emissions. However, recent discussions have questioned the applicability of using this climate metric across ruminant livestock production systems where short-lived biogenic CH₄ emissions are a substantial component of total GHG, and modeled scenarios imply ambitious emission reductions and the analysis requires alignment with temperature changes (e.g., Ridoutt, 2021; Costa et al., 2022; Pressman et al., 2023). The use of GWP* as a complement to the GWP100 metric could be particularly relevant when assessing the potential impact on additional temperature from applying AMFA or other CH₄-based mitigation strategies compared with other strategies that reduce long-lived GHG (e.g., CO₂ or N₂O) or when considering that some CH₄-based mitigation strategies have been found to reduce CH₄ (short-lived

GHG) at the expense of increasing other long-lived GHG (del Prado et al., 2023).

At a supranational scale of the European FAO region of dairy sheep, del Prado et al. (2021) tested the long-term effect (in 20, 40, 60, and 80 yr) of different rates of introduction of 3-NOP as an enteric CH₄ mitigation measure on CO₂ warming equivalents (using GWP* metrics), assuming a persistent 30% reduction of enteric CH₄. The speed of introduction particularly affected the near-term effect on additional warming but with similar effects over a 100-yr horizon.

Recommendations

- Clear documentation is recommended on what standpoint is taken on efficacy (based on what evidence) when estimating the enteric CH₄ mitigation potential of the combination of different AMFA, particularly of AMFA with different modes of actions and diets and delivery methods.
- Assumptions on the additivity of efficacies should follow insights from experimental work, and in the future, potentially from models as these continue to develop in the search for capturing combined AMFA efficacy and effectiveness.

Life Cycle Assessment

Although various AMFA have shown efficacy in reducing enteric CH₄ emissions in experimental conditions (Durmic et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025), it is also important that GHG emissions are evaluated across the full production system from a life cycle perspective (Beauchemin et al., 2022; Fouts et al., 2022; Firkins and Mitchell, 2023). In this sense, although the inclusion of AMFA will lead to a reduction in short-lived CH₄ emissions, on some occasions it can imply a modest increase in long-lived emissions such as CO₂ and N₂O through some level of intensification (e.g., as seen for *Asparagopsis taxiformis* in Ridoutt et al., 2022), changes in N metabolism, and emissions associated with AMFA production and transport. This is an importance nuance, because each molecule of CH₄ will be removed from the atmosphere within about a decade compared with hundreds and thousands of years for N₂O and CO₂, respectively. Although emissions related to the production and transport of these AMFA must be included in an LCA study (FAO, 2020), they are rarely accounted for. The resulting impact is a near-term reduction in warming, but the additional long-lived emissions make the longer-term goal of climate stabilization more difficult (del Prado et al., 2023). This temporal trade-off is not apparent when results are reported using the GWP100

climate metric, but it is a very relevant consideration for climate policy and action (FAO, 2023).

Although proven successful for reducing enteric CH₄ emission, further environmental impacts from AMFA are yet to be fully studied. The production, processing, and distribution of some AMFA might lead to additional emissions and other effects (e.g., *Asparagopsis* sp. and marine ecosystem disturbance; upstream effects). Added to these effects, the inclusion of bromoform-containing seaweeds in ruminant diets has shown to adversely affect ruminal VFA production, feed intake, and animal productivity (Camer-Pesci et al., 2023), with bromoform in *A. taxiformis* as the most likely cause of rumen wall inflammation and transfer to urine and milk (Muizelaar et al., 2021).

To date, studies from a life cycle perspective are relatively few. When comparing AMFA, results indicate a large variation in outcomes depending on the assumptions made, AMFA delivery method, and the type of production system involved. Alvarez-Hess et al. (2019) used LCA to evaluate the use of AMFA in selected Australian and Canadian beef and dairy production systems. At the farm gate, the GHG emissions intensity of milk (kg CO₂-eq/kg fat and protein corrected milk; **FPCM**) assessed using the GWP100 climate metric, was reduced by up to 19%, although reductions varied among farms and depended on the length of time the AMFA was used. This study assumed GHG emissions associated with 3-NOP production of 47.9 kg CO₂-eq/kg of 3-NOP. For beef, the farm gate GHG emissions (kg CO₂-eq/kg of live weight) were reduced by up to 22%, with results varying across farms and with length of time the AMFA was used. Overall, the enteric CH₄ emission reductions far exceeded the additional emissions associated with additive production when assessed using the GWP100 climate metric. In other LCA studies involving 3-NOP, Feng and Kebreab (2020) reported GHG emissions reductions of almost 12% for milk produced in California, assuming 3-NOP was supplied to lactating cows only. Because there was a 39% reduction of CH₄ emission in lactating cows, this result shows the effects of assumptions of how and where 3-NOP is used on-farm. Similarly, Uddin et al. (2022) reported a 12% GHG emission reduction for milk produced in confined feeding systems across the United States. In another study involving the use of 3-NOP for beef production in Colombia, Arango et al. (2022) reported reductions in GHG emissions intensity (kg CO₂-eq/kg of live weight) of up to 24%.

On the use of nitrates, the GHG emissions associated with the production of calcium nitrate are reportedly around 1.76 kg CO₂-eq/kg of calcium nitrate (Alvarez-Hess et al., 2019) which is >20 times lower than for 3-NOP. However, the dosage rates administered are more than a hundred times higher, meaning that the GHG

emissions associated with production of the nitrate end product can be many times higher than that of 3-NOP. Nevertheless, LCA studies report net GHG emissions reduction benefits from the use of nitrate as an AMFA when assessed using the GWP100 climate metric. At the farm gate, Alvarez-Hess et al. (2019) reported net GHG emission reduction benefits of up to 9% for milk production (kg CO₂-eq/kg of FPCM) and between 0.9% and 8.6% for beef cattle production (kg CO₂-eq/kg of live weight). This compares with a reduction of 2.7% to 4.5% for milk production in California (Feng and Kebreab, 2020). In another dairy study, Uddin et al. (2022) reported farm gate GHG emissions reductions for milk of 4.8%. Overall, the efficacy of enteric CH₄ abatement from the use of nitrates is lower compared with 3-NOP

In the case of another class of potent AMFA known as trihalomethanes (bromoform), as a major component in the red seaweed *A. taxiformis*, commercial production is still scaling up and less is known about the GHG emissions associated with cultivation, processing, and distribution. In one study, GHG emissions were estimated to be on the order of 2.0 kg CO₂-eq per g of bromoform active ingredient (Ridoutt et al., 2022). However, this value could vary considerably, depending on the method of macroalgae cultivation and its location, as well as the method used to process the fresh algal material into a product that is suitable for distribution to livestock producers, and which avoids loss of the bioactive compound (Nilsson and Martin, 2022). Notwithstanding the potential for GHG emissions associated with supply of the AMFA to be reduced substantially, these emissions appear large compared with those of both 3-NOP and nitrate. However, with *A. taxiformis* the reported enteric CH₄ emission reductions are also generally larger and LCA has demonstrated net GHG emission reduction benefits when assessed using the GWP100 climate metric (Ridoutt et al., 2022). In a prospective LCA study of use in Australian beef cattle feedlots, the emissions from the feedlot sector were reduced by 12% to 40%, and overall, the emissions from the Australian beef cattle industry were reduced by 1% to 4% (Ridoutt et al., 2022), which represents a significant reduction of 0.6 to 2.0 Mt CO₂-eq. The difference between these 2 sectors is most likely explained by the mainly pasture- and rangeland-based production systems used in Australia where viable methods for delivering the AMFA are still under development.

What aforementioned LCA-based studies on various AMFA demonstrate is that the benefits from GHG emission reduction are highly variable. Variability exists in the degree of enteric CH₄ emission reduction, dependent on AMFA type and inclusion rate in the diet, the feeding management and method of AMFA delivery, and composition of the feed ration (Belanche et al., 2025; Dijkstra et al., 2025). This means this variability is best

addressed carefully in any LCA study instead of adopting generic values and estimates. Furthermore, some regulatory aspects are involved, such as recommended dosing of a single animal, delivery method, additive storage, and the dietary and production conditions involved (Tricarico et al., 2025). The GHG abatement benefits are also dependent on the characteristics of the production system and the animal life stage during which AMFA are included, which hence have to be defined carefully in any LCA. The ability to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions consistently for most AMFA in grazing systems remains quite uncertain because a delivery method of bioactive components that ensures interaction with rumen microbiota when the feed material is fermented is very challenging and still requires further development (Hristov et al., 2025). The most consistent results are reported in the dairy industry (automated or controlled feeding systems in particular) where daily administration is feasible and may be assumed either across an entire herd or only during lactation. More variable results are reported for beef cattle production systems because many results include periods of extensive grazing where solutions for viable AMFA administration other than salt and molasses lick blocks, boluses, or in drinking water, are not yet available (Hegarty et al., 2021). To a lesser extent, given the possibility of automated feeding while in the milking shed or offered silage on pads or in the paddock, variable abatement would also be expected for grazing dairy cattle. And even on the assumption of adequate efficacy of AMFA such as 3-NOP and *Asparagopsis*, very limited evidence indicates enteric CH₄ abatement when these are consumed intermittently by free-ranging ruminants (Hegarty et al., 2021). The life cycle perspective is therefore critical for an integral assessment, and much care is needed before extrapolating results from one production context to another.

Another aspect to consider is the animal category (young vs. mature livestock, lactating vs. dry) within a given farm type in terms of differential efficacy levels and limitations to apply in some of the categories by the authorizing regulation body. For example, replacement animals in a dairy cattle farm contribute to 20%–30% of the total enteric CH₄ emissions (Grandl et al., 2019). Whether an AMFA can be applied only to lactating animals or also to young stock would make a big difference in the overall farm emissions.

Recommendations

- Consider all relevant environmental impact categories to track the potential synergies and trade-offs of GHG reduction with other LCA impact categories.
- More holistic approaches, such as LCA methods, require a full accounting of the off-farm emissions

associated with the production and transport of these AMFA. FAO (2020) provides a full chapter with recommendations on how to assess the environmental impacts arising from the life stage of manufacturing of feed additives. Also provided are general aspects on the life cycle inventory.

- Take special care and report assessment limitations when extrapolating AMFA results from one livestock system to another, when AMFA is provided for a limited period within a selected life stage of the animal, or when AMFA allows modification of the diet composition and affects feed efficiency and emissions other than enteric CH₄.
- Report assessment limitations when AMFA changes feed intake, diet composition, milk and meat production and composition, and excreted OM, volatile solids, and N.
- When making assumptions regarding the additivity of efficacies, it is recommended to draw insights from experimental studies. As models evolve to capture the combined efficacy and effectiveness of AMFA, they may also provide valuable information for future estimations.

UNCERTAINTIES

What Can We Learn from Meta-Analyses?

Although efficacy of AMFA was relatively high numerically compared with other measures (Arndt et al., 2022; Congio et al., 2021), it has to be reminded that this outcome originates from trials performed under rather controlled conditions and therefore it does not account for uncertainty associated with actual application in practice and usage in commercial feeding management (efficacy vs. effectiveness). The latter is a relevant and additional point of evaluation that needs to be addressed when adopting the outcomes of meta-analyses and empirical modeling, or even of mechanistic modeling (Dijkstra et al., 2025) with any attempt to implement the effect of AMFA in farm assessment and inventory tools.

Prediction equations developed for AMFA can be implemented in farm assessment tools and inventory methodology, and they can also deliver an estimate of the uncertainty associated with predicted efficacy values. Next to the dosage of the AMFA applied, such equations generally require additional explanatory variables, which involves information that would perhaps also be generally available in farm assessment tools or national inventory methodology. This information includes level of feed intake, type of diet, chemical composition of the diet, animal type, and animal productivity (Dijkstra et al., 2018; Feng et al., 2020), in a very similar way as used in meta-analysis for various types of ruminants on

enteric CH₄ emission without a focus on AMFA (Niu et al., 2018; van Lingen et al., 2019; Belanche et al., 2023). Some of this information has been used for the most recent update of the IPCC Guidelines for estimation of enteric CH₄ (IPCC, 2019).

Uncertainty in these explanatory variables, or model inputs, contributes significantly to estimates of uncertainty, which came forward from an uncertainty analysis performed with a mechanistic model as a Tier 3 approach indicating a 15% uncertainty for predicted CH₄ production (13% for CH₄ yield) compared with 20% adopted by IPCC (IPCC, 2019). Meta-analyses indicate a similar order of magnitude of uncertainty that can be expected for the uncertainty of estimated efficacy of an AMFA as derived for nitrate (Feng et al., 2020) and 3-NOP (Dijkstra et al., 2018) in beef and lactating cattle. The standard error for the coefficient of effect of additive dosage on the estimated percentage reduction in enteric CH₄ production was 15% and 21%, respectively (20% confirmed in an update by Kebreab et al., 2023, for lactating cow data only). These uncertainties hold presuming the applied additive dosage is precisely known, which in itself has an uncertainty as well.

Irrespective of the uncertainty involved, the scientific background and insights coming from meta-analyses as an empirical approach, or from more detailed models, can definitely be adopted in tools of farm GHG assessment, C accounting, and national GHG and N inventory (Dijkstra et al., 2025). If the effect of an AMFA on enteric CH₄ is exerted with full certainty within the rumen environment, the outcomes of meta-analysis in principle indicates best knowledge of what to expect based on available empirical data. Main uncertainties to address, but not coming forward from these meta-analyses, are rather related to the method of allocation of the AMFA to the animal, its inclusion in the diet, and the rumen fermentation conditions met with feeding (where the additive exerts its effect on CH₄). All these aspects may deviate from those encountered with the empirical database used for meta-analysis. It is recommended to keep the mode of action in mind when evaluating the relative importance of these aspects for uncertainty.

A complicating factor to directly applying equations derived from meta-analysis is that the method of AMFA application and (temporal) changes in feeding management in practice can be less than ideal than for the experimental database from which these equations were derived from. To minimize variation in additive treatment and to maximize the power of the study, AMFA are normally included into a TMR, animals are fed at the same moment, and diet composition is controlled as much as possible. With application of the AMFA in practice this will not be the case, and a noncontinuous intake of the

additive, a dosage varying within a day and across days or weeks, may lead to a different outcome of efficacy than anticipated from these meta-analyses. The extent to which this affects AMFA efficacy probably depends on its mode of action. For example, with 3-NOP it has been well demonstrated that pulse dosing (mimicking an intake twice daily) only leads to temporary reductions in CH₄ emissions (Reynolds et al., 2014). Efficacy of nitrate might be less dependent on these dynamics, and it will be rather the extent to which ingested nitrate becomes reduced to ammonium that determines efficacy (Olijhoek et al., 2016). On the other hand, for AMFA with a less direct impact on methanogenesis (various plant extracts, including essential oils, tannins, saponins; Belanche et al., 2025), variation in dosing, and method of application may be more relevant because trade-offs relative to feed intake and feed digestibility easily occur, and sticking to the recommended dosing (with a relatively small tolerance range) is a prerequisite (van Gastelen et al., 2023). The lower-than-expected success rate of CH₄ mitigation in studies is indicative of the complexity of using these AMFA (Berça et al., 2023). This means that for this category of AMFA, details on actual application method under practical conditions are most likely to be determinants of efficacy and hence have to be accounted for as well (Hegarty et al., 2021).

Clear documentation of the origin and accuracy of activity data is needed, including dosage and allowance to animals, inclusion in the diet, animal type involved, and even season. Equally, consensus on mode of action as well as existence and insight in causes of variation in AMFA efficacy, are all needed to make choices on how to account for the effect including its uncertainty. The mode of action of the AMFA will certainly affect the sources and level of the uncertainties associated with quantifying its efficacy, therefore the uncertainties analysis and the assumptions made must be tailored to each type of AMFA. Data may be available for the amount of AMFA being purchased and for the average yearly diet, but this does not specify the dosage used for certain animals at a specific moment in time in reality. It requires a separate documentation in itself on how level of aggregation that is adopted in tools for farm assessments, C accounting, and national GHG inventory compares to available survey data on farm management and AMFA application and amounts being purchased. At least a quantitative view and argumentation is required on how much on-farm reality in terms of applied dosage, estimated AMFA efficacy, animal groups or categories, and concurrent production conditions may deviate from the ideal conditions that are met in AMFA studies reported in the literature.

A further complication is that with a direct application of equations derived from meta-analysis, it is inherently

presumed that the level of application is the same as the level these equations have been derived for. But the animal as the experimental unit in *in vivo* efficacy trials is not the same as that of an “aggregated” animal adopted in accounting. Often, information and details from surveys are aggregated into a yearly statistic of the average herd composition, animal productivity, and overall feed requirements (often based on feeding tables and analyses of purchased feeds and roughages by commercial labs). Hence, a budgeting approach for the average conditions met at a farm, region, or nation are used in a very similar manner as described under IPCC Tier 2 methodology (IPCC, 2019).

Mechanistic Modeling Versus Meta-Analysis

More detailed mechanistic models may deliver valuable in-depth understanding of the mode of action and variation in AMFA efficacy (Dijkstra et al., 2025). These models may aid in a more accurate prediction of not only (variation in) AMFA efficacy but also in reducing uncertainty. Currently, direct or indirect application of such mechanistic modeling approaches is lacking, and for the time being farm assessment tools and inventory methodology have to rely on outcomes from meta-analyses of efficacy trials (Dijkstra et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025). Although a strong empirical database used for meta-analyses contributes to prediction capacity, the approach suffers from some limitations less imperative for mechanistic modeling. First, applicability of meta-analyses outcomes may not be valid outside the boundaries of the database they originate from, with respect to diets, feeding management and production levels, and animal type, as well as delivery method of the AMFA. Second, because meta-analyses do not represent a mechanism, trends in AMFA efficacy may be more difficult to predict. Third, meta-analyses are typically focused on a single AMFA, and performing them for combinations of different AMFA will prove to be not only far more complex, but almost impossible because a database for the combined use of AMFA is lacking. Fourth, meta-analyses appear less capable of quantifying trade-offs or co-benefits, for which other specific meta-analyses would have to be applied, in contrast to a more integral approach that could be done with mechanistic modeling.

Sole Effects Versus Combined Effects

Finally, and somewhat associated with the third point made in the previous section, an even larger uncertainty exists to the mitigating effect to be expected when different AMFA are combined, making use of different modes of actions simultaneously (Belanche et al., 2025; Hristov et al., 2025). Experimental work has tested different

combinations of AMFA, for example, supplementing a blend of essential oils alone or in rotation with lauric acid across 3 experimental periods (Klop et al., 2017) or combining 3-NOP with monensin (Romero-Perez et al., 2014) or nitrate (Maigaard et al., 2024), but information is still very scarce in this area. Meta-analyses have yet to provide an indication of what to expect and how to account for this as more data become available. The main principles of AMFA mode of action will hold across feeding conditions, production levels, and species and breeds. The extent of the efficacy may vary, however, with diet and feeding management, and there may be interactions between different AMFA, although the few studies reported did not show interactions (e.g., van Zijderveld et al., 2010; Hristov et al., 2025).

Recommendations

- Provide clear documentation on how to align the aggregated data used with the basis of the applied prediction model for feed efficacy.
- It is not possible to offer specific recommendations for overcoming limitations associated with the application of equations derived from meta-analysis. However, mechanistic modeling may help reduce uncertainties and improve tools for farm GHG assessment, C accounting, and GHG inventory. This is due to the limited research on the effect of multiple AMFA, the lack of a comprehensive database on the use of combinations of different AMFA, and the inability of meta-analyses to effectively quantify trade-offs and co-benefits compared with a mechanistic modeling approach.
- Unless a sufficiently large empirical database becomes available that includes all combinations of AMFA for several dosages, a mechanistic approach based on rumen fermentation conditions and response in microbial and methanogen activity (Dijkstra et al., 2025) may help out in finding ways to quantify abatement at the least occurrence and the direction to expect for such interactions, and preferably aid in quantifying these interactions.

BEYOND ENTERIC METHANE ABATEMENT

Besides the enteric CH₄ mitigating effect, AMFA have the potential to affect GHG emissions in a variety of ways, including downstream changes in feed intake, ADG, or milk production, N excretion and manure, as well as upstream emissions from their production and distribution. Sometimes, AMFA can lead to trade-offs or leakages or act synergistically toward reducing other GHG or N emissions. Downstream effects will depend on the AMFA chosen. For example, the use of 3-NOP seems

to have a straightforward effect on inhibiting the enzyme responsible for CH₄ formation, and feed efficiency seems to be improved through the increased production of milk fat or milk protein (van Gastelen et al., 2024). Other additives, such as a fat supplement, may reduce CH₄ emissions at the animal level, but can lead to larger CH₄ emissions at the manure storage level if it increases the CH₄ production potential of the organic matter in animal feces (Petersen et al., 2013), but in contrast, fat supplementation can be a strategy to improve N use efficiency and reduce N excretion (Nichols et al., 2018). It has also been shown to improve the fatty acid profile in milk and increase animal welfare levels (del Prado et al., 2010).

For scenarios where a strategy to introduce AMFA implies large-scale changes (e.g., if AMFA production would increase the use of feed co-products on a large scale and for which the supply is limited), the analysis would have to account for market limitations and reactions (Blonk et al., 2021). In this type of scenario where the economic allocation is greatly affected, it becomes more reasonable to use a cLCA modeling approach, thus expanding system boundaries, rather than the commonly used aLCA approach. These types of challenges and decisions would also apply to scenarios such as those implying large-scale cultivation of bromoform-containing seaweed (Nilsson and Martin, 2022) instead of adding bromoform as a compound. In addition, potential for changes in industry structure exists if production practices shift toward systems that are more amenable to AMFA administration, which deserves accounting in its own right.

Recommendation

- It is recommended that next to the accounting of enteric CH₄ mitigating effects and associated synergies and trade-offs at the animal level, synergies, and trade-offs on GHG emissions are considered at levels prior and subsequent (upstream and downstream) to the animal to determine the full effect of AMFA use. Moreover, full effects should be considered according to legislative and regulatory bodies (Tricarico et al., 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

The accounting of on-farm enteric CH₄ emissions and benefits from the use of AMFA starts with the ruminant animal, and goes all the way to national and supranational accounting. The enteric CH₄ abatement from the use of AMFA per se, however, remains to be fully quantified in most accounting systems and scales. In the accounting of AMFA abatement, it is critical to consider the implications of efficacy (results from controlled interventions) versus effectiveness (results from real-world conditions).

The accounting of synergies and trade-offs in GHG emissions at levels both upstream and downstream of the animal need to be considered. This will help determine the full effect of AMFA use. Furthermore, these full effects should be assessed in accordance with legislative and regulatory bodies.

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: 3-NOP = 3-nitrooxypropanol; aLCA = attributional life cycle assessment; AMFA = antimethanogenic feed additives; cLCA = consequential life cycle assessment; CO₂-eq = carbon dioxide equivalents; DE = digestible energy; DOM = digested organic matter; EF = emission factor; ETS = emissions trading schemes; *f* = function of; FPCM = fat- and protein-corrected milk; GEI = gross energy intake; GWP = global warming potential; IQR = interquartile range; ISO = International Standards Organization; LCA = life cycle assessment; LMIC = low- and middle-income countries; NDC = nationally determined contributions; Reg. = regression; Y_m = methane conversion factor.

REFERENCES

- Almeida, A. K., F. C. Cowley, and R. S. Hegarty. 2023. A regional-scale assessment of nutritional-system strategies for abatement of enteric methane from grazing livestock. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 63:1461–1472. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN22315>.
- Almeida, A. K., R. S. Hegarty, and A. Cowie. 2021. Meta-analysis quantifying the potential of dietary additives and rumen modifiers for methane mitigation in ruminant production systems. *Anim. Nutr.* 7:1219–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2021.09.005>.
- Alvarez-Hess, P. S., S. M. Little, P. J. Moate, J. L. Jacobs, K. A. Beauchemin, and R. J. Eckard. 2019. A partial life cycle assessment of the greenhouse gas mitigation potential of feeding 3-nitrooxypropanol and nitrate to cattle. *Agric. Syst.* 169:14–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2018.11.008>.
- Arango, J., M. Bastidas, C. Costa Jr., R. González, A. Marin, N. Matiz, A. Ruden, and D. Villegas. 2022. Carbon footprint and mitigation scenarios for Hacienda San Jose: Identifying opportunities and challenges using a consolidated modelling framework. Final Report. International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Cali, Colombia. Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/121105>.
- Arndt, C., A. N. Hristov, W. J. Price, S. C. McClelland, A. M. Pelaez, S. F. Cueva, J. Oh, J. Dijkstra, A. Bannink, A. R. Bayat, L. A. Crompton, M. A. Eugene, D. Enahoro, E. Kebreab, M. Kreuzer, M. McGee, C. Martin, C. J. Newbold, C. K. Reynolds, A. Schwarm, K. J. Shingfield, J. B. Veneman, D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz, and Z. Yu. 2022. Full adoption of the most effective strategies to mitigate methane emissions by ruminants can help meet the 1.5°C target by 2030 but not 2050. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 119:e2111294119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2111294119>.
- Australian Government. 2023. Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions in beef cattle through feeding nitrate containing supplements method. Accessed Oct. 20, 2023. <https://www.dceew.gov.au/climate-change/emissions-reduction/emissions-reduction-fund/methods/reducing-greenhouse-gas-emissions-in-beef-cattle-through-feeding-nitrate-containing-supplements>.
- Bannink, A., W. J. Spek, J. Dijkstra, and L. B. J. Šebek. 2018. A Tier 3 method for enteric methane in dairy cows applied for fecal N digestibility in the ammonia inventory. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 2:66. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2018.00066>.
- Bannink, A., M. W. van Schijndel, and J. Dijkstra. 2011. A model of enteric fermentation in dairy cows to estimate methane emission for the Dutch National Inventory Report using the IPCC Tier 3 approach. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167:603–618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2011.04.043>.
- Beauchemin, K. A., and E. J. McGeough. 2013. Life Cycle Assessment in Ruminant Production. CABI Books. CABI. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781780640426.0212>.
- Beauchemin, K. A., E. M. Ungerfeld, A. L. Abdalla, C. Alvarez, C. Arndt, P. Becquet, C. Benchaar, A. Berndt, R. M. Mauricio, T. A. McAllister, W. Oyhantcabal, S. A. Salami, L. Shalloo, Y. Sun, J. Tricarico, A. Uwizeye, C. De Camillis, M. Bernoux, T. Robinson, and E. Kebreab. 2022. *Invited review: Current enteric methane mitigation options.* *J. Dairy Sci.* 105:9297–9326. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22091>.
- Belanche, A., A. Bannink, J. Dijkstra, Z. Durmic, F. Garcia, F. G. Santos, S. Huws, J. Jeyanathan, P. Lund, R. I. Mackie, T. A. McAllister, D. P. Morgavi, S. Muetzel, D. W. Pitta, D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz, and E. M. Ungerfeld. 2025. Feed additives for methane mitigation: A guideline to uncover the mode of action of antimethanogenic feed additives for ruminants. *J. Dairy Sci.* 108:375–394. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25046>.
- Belanche, A., A. N. Hristov, H. J. van Lingen, S. E. Denman, E. Kebreab, A. Schwarm, M. Kreuzer, M. Niu, M. Eugène, V. Niderkorn, C. Martin, H. Archimède, M. McGee, C. K. Reynolds, L. A. Crompton, A. R. Bayat, Z. Yu, A. Bannink, J. Dijkstra, A. V. Chaves, H. Clark, S. Muetzel, V. Lind, J. M. Moorby, J. A. Rooke, A. Aubry, W. Antezana, M. Wang, R. Hegarty, V. Hutton Oddy, J. Hill, P. E. Vercoe, J. V. Savian, A. L. Abdalla, Y. A. Soltan, A. L. Gomes Monteiro, J. C. Ku-Vera, G. Jaurena, C. A. Gómez-Bravo, O. L. Mayorga, G. F. S. Congio, and D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz. 2023. Prediction of enteric methane emissions by sheep using an intercontinental database. *J. Clean. Prod.* 384:135523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135523>.
- Berça, A. S., L. O. Tedeschi, A. da Silva Cardoso, and R. A. Reis. 2023. Meta-analysis of the relationship between dietary condensed tannins and methane emissions by cattle. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 298:115564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2022.115564>.
- Beukes, P. C., P. Gregorini, and A. J. Romera. 2011. Estimating greenhouse gas emissions from New Zealand dairy systems using a mechanistic whole farm model and inventory methodology. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167:708–720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeeds.2011.04.050>.
- Blonk, H., H. Bosch, N. Braconi, S. Van Cauwenberghe, and B. Kok. 2021. The applicability of LCA guidelines to model the effects of feed additives on the environmental footprint of animal production. Blonk Consultants and DSM Nutritional Products.
- Cain, M., J. Lynch, M. R. Allen, J. S. Fuglestvedt, D. J. Frame, and A. H. Macey. 2019. Improved calculation of warming-equivalent emissions for short-lived climate pollutants. *NPJ Clim. Atmos. Sci.* 2:29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-019-0086-4>.
- Camer-Pesci, B., D. W. Laird, M. van Keulen, A. Vadiveloo, M. Chalmers, and N. R. Moheimani. 2023. Opportunities of *Asparagopsis* sp. cultivation to reduce methanogenesis in ruminants: A critical review. *Algal Res.* 76:103308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2023.103308>.
- Colomb, V., M. Bernoux, L. Bockel, J.-L. Chotte, S. Martin, C. Martin-Phipps, J. Mousset, M. Tinlot, and O. Touchemoulin. 2012. Review of GHG calculators in agriculture and forestry sectors: A guideline for appropriate choice and use of landscape based tools. Version 2.0. Agence de l'Environnement et de la Maîtrise de l'Energie (ADEME, French Agency for Environment and Energy Management), Institut de Recherche pour le développement (IRD, French Research Institute for Development) and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/ex_act/pdf/ADEME/Review_existingGHGtool_VF_UK4.pdf.
- Colombini, S., A. R. Graziosi, G. Galassi, G. Gislon, G. M. Crovetto, D. Enriquez-Hidalgo, and L. Rapetti. 2023. Evaluation of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) equations to predict enteric methane emission from lactating cows fed Mediterranean diets. *JDS Commun.* 4:181–185. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jdsc.2022-0240>.
- Congio, G. F. S., A. Bannink, O. L. Mayorga Mogollón, G. Jaurena, H. Gonda, J. I. Gere, M. E. Cerón-Cucchi, A. Ortiz-Chura, M. P. Tieri, O. Hernández, P. Ricci, M. P. Juliarena, B. Lombardi, A. L. Abdalla, A. L. Abdalla-Filho, A. Berndt, P. P. A. Oliveira, F. L. Henrique, A. L. G. Monteiro, L. I. Borges, H. M. N. Ribeiro-Filho, L. G. R. Pereira, T. R. Tomich, M. M. Campos, F. S. Machado, M. I. Marccondes, M. E. Z. Mercadante, L. S. Sakamoto, L. G. Albuquerque, P. C. F. Carvalho, J. Rossetto, J. V. Savian, P. H. M. Rodrigues, F. P. Júnior, T. S. Moreira, R. M. Mauricio, J. P. Pacheco Rodrigues, A. L. C. B. Borges, R. Reis e Silva, H. F. Lage, R. A. Reis, A. C. Ruggieri, A. S. Cardoso, S. C. da Silva, M. B. Chiavegato, S. C. Valadares-Filho, F. A. S. Silva, D. Zanetti, T. T. Berchielli, J. D. Messana, C. Muñoz, C. J. Ariza-Nieto, A. M. Sierra-Alarcón, L. B. Gualdrón-Duarte, L. I. Mestra-Vargas, I. C. Molina-Botero, R. Barahona-Rosales, J. Arango, X. Gaviria-Urbe, L. A. Giraldo Valderrama, J. R. Rosero-Noguera, S. L. Posada-Ochoa, S. Abarca-Monge, R. Soto-Blanco, J. C. Ku-Vera, R. Jiménez-Ocampo, E. J. Flores-Santiago, O. A. Castelán-Ortega, M. F. Vázquez-Carrillo, M. Benaouda, C. A. Gómez-Bravo, V. I. A. Bolovich, M. A. D. Céspedes, L. Astigaraga, and A. N. Hristov. 2021. Enteric methane mitigation strategies for ruminant livestock systems in the Latin America and Caribbean region: A meta-analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* 312:127693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127693>.
- Costa, C. Jr., E. Wollenberg, M. Benitez, R. Newman, N. Gardner, and F. Bellone. 2022. Roadmap for achieving net-zero emissions in global food systems by 2050. *Sci. Rep.* 12:15064. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-18601-1>.
- Cowie, A., R. Eckard, and S. Eady. 2012. Greenhouse gas accounting for inventory, emissions trading and life cycle assessment in the land-based sector: A review. *Crop Pasture Sci.* 63:284–296. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CP11188>.

- Crosson, P., L. Shalloo, D. O'Brien, G. J. Lanigan, P. A. Foley, T. M. Boland, and D. A. Kenny. 2011. A review of whole farm systems models of greenhouse gas emissions from beef and dairy cattle production systems. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167:29–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.04.001>.
- Crumpler, K., R. Abi Khalil, E. Tanganelli, N. Rai, L. Roffredi, A. Meybeck, V. Umulisa, J. Wolf, and M. Bernoux. 2021. (Interim) Global update report—Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries in the Nationally Determined Contributions. Environment and Natural Resources Management Working Paper No. 91. FAO, Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb7442en>.
- de Ondarza, M. B., A. N. Hristov, and J. M. Tricarico. 2023. A global dataset of enteric methane mitigation experiments with lactating and non-lactating dairy cows conducted from 1963 to 2022. *Data Brief* 49:109459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109459>.
- de Vries, M., and I. J. M. de Boer. 2010. Comparing environmental impacts for livestock products: A review of life cycle assessments. *Livest. Sci.* 128:1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2009.11.007>.
- del Prado, A., D. Chadwick, L. Cardenas, T. Misselbrook, D. Scholefield, and P. Merino. 2010. Exploring systems responses to mitigation of GHG in UK dairy farms. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 136:318–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2009.09.015>.
- del Prado, A., P. Crosson, J. E. Olesen, and C. A. Rotz. 2013. Whole-farm models to quantify greenhouse gas emissions and their potential use for linking climate change mitigation and adaptation in temperate grassland ruminant-based farming systems. *Animal* 7:373–385. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731113000748>.
- del Prado, A., J. Lynch, S. Liu, B. Ridoutt, G. Pardo, and F. Mitloehner. 2023. Animal board invited review: Opportunities and challenges in using GWP* to report the impact of ruminant livestock on global temperature change. *Animal* 17:100790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2023.100790>.
- del Prado, A., P. Manzano, and G. Pardo. 2021. The role of the European small ruminant dairy sector in stabilising global temperatures: Lessons from GWP* warming-equivalent emission metrics. *J. Dairy Res.* 88:8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022029921000157>.
- del Prado, A., T. Misselbrook, D. Chadwick, A. Hopkins, R. J. Dewhurst, P. Davison, A. Butler, J. Schroder, and D. Scholefield. 2011. SIMS(DAIRY): A modelling framework to identify sustainable dairy farms in the UK. Framework description and test for organic systems and N fertiliser optimisation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 409:3993–4009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.05.050>.
- Dijkstra, J., A. Bannink, G. F. S. Congio, J. L. Ellis, M. Eugène, F. Garcia, M. Niu, R. E. Vibart, D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz, and E. Kebreab. 2025. Feed additives for methane mitigation: Modeling the impact of feed additives on enteric methane emission of ruminants—Approaches and recommendations. *J. Dairy Sci.* 108:356–374. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25049>.
- Dijkstra, J., A. Bannink, J. France, E. Kebreab, and S. van Gastelen. 2018. *Short communication*: Antimethanogenic effects of 3-nitroxypropanol depend on supplementation dose, dietary fiber content, and cattle type. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101:9041–9047. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2018-14456>.
- Dijkstra, J., J. France, and D. R. Davies. 1998. Different mathematical approaches to estimating microbial protein supply in ruminants. *J. Dairy Sci.* 81:3370–3384.
- Durmic, Z., E. C. Duin, A. Bannink, A. Belanche, V. Carbone, M. D. Carro, M. Crüsemann, V. Fievez, F. Garcia, A. Hristov, M. Joch, G. Martinez-Fernandez, S. Muetzel, E. M. Ungerfeld, M. Wang, and D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz. 2025. Feed additives for methane mitigation: Recommendations for identification and selection of bioactive compounds to develop antimethanogenic feed additives. *J. Dairy Sci.* 108:302–321. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25045>.
- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). 2020. Environmental performance of feed additives in livestock supply chains—Guidelines for assessment—Version 1. Livestock Environmental Assessment and Performance Partnership (FAO LEAP). Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy. Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/bbe7a216-98db-4aa9-aa52-b8c837be5907>.
- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). 2023. Methane emissions in livestock and rice systems—Sources, quantification, mitigation and metrics. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy. Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc7607en>.
- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) and GRA (Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases). 2020. Livestock Activity Data Guidance (L-ADG): Methods and guidance on compilation of activity data for Tier 2 livestock GHG inventories. FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca7510en>.
- Feng, X. Y., J. Dijkstra, A. Bannink, S. van Gastelen, J. France, and E. Kebreab. 2020. Antimethanogenic effects of nitrate supplementation in cattle: A meta-analysis. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103:11375–11385. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2020-18541>.
- Feng, X., and E. Kebreab. 2020. Net reductions in greenhouse gas emissions from feed additive use in California dairy cattle. *PLoS One* 15:e0234289. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234289>.
- Firkins, J. L., and K. E. Mitchell. 2023. *Invited review*: Rumen modifiers in today's dairy rations. *J. Dairy Sci.* 106:3053–3071. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22644>.
- Flachowsky, G., and J. Kamphues. 2012. Carbon footprints for food of animal origin: What are the most preferable criteria to measure animal yields? *Animals (Basel)* 2:108–126. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani2020108>.
- Fouts, J. Q., M. C. Honan, B. M. Roque, J. M. Tricarico, and E. Kebreab. 2022. Enteric methane mitigation interventions. *Transl. Anim. Sci.* 6:txac041. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tas/txac041>.
- Giger-Reverdin, S., P. Morand-Fehr, and G. Tran. 2003. Literature survey of the influence of dietary fat composition on methane production in dairy cattle. *Livest. Prod. Sci.* 82:73–79. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226\(03\)00002-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226(03)00002-2).
- Grainger, C., and K. A. Beauchemin. 2011. Can enteric methane emissions from ruminants be lowered without lowering their production? *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 166–167:308–320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.04.021>.
- Grandl, F., M. Furger, M. Kreuzer, and M. Zehetmeier. 2019. Impact of longevity on greenhouse gas emissions and profitability of individual dairy cows analysed with different system boundaries. *Animal* 13:198–208. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S175173111800112X>.
- Guinée, J. B., M. Gorrée, R. Heijungs, G. Huppes, R. Kleijn, A. de Koning, L. van Oers, A. Wegener Sleswijk, S. Suh, H. A. Udo de Haes, H. de Bruijn, R. van Duin, M. A. J. Huijbregts, E. Lindeijer, A. A. H. Roorda, B. L. van der Ven, and B. P. Weidema. 2002. Handbook on Life Cycle Assessment. Operational guide to the ISO Standards. 1. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Hegarty, R. S., R. A. Cortez Passetti, K. M. Dittmer, Y. Wang, S. Shelton, J. Emmet-Booth, E. Wollenberg, T. McAllister, S. Leahy, K. A. Beauchemin, and N. Gurwick. 2021. An evaluation of emerging feed additives to reduce methane emissions from livestock. Edition 1. Report coordinated by Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS) and the New Zealand Agricultural Greenhouse Gas Research Centre (NZAGRC) initiative of the Global Research Alliance (GRA). Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/116489>.
- Hellwing, A. L. F., M. R. Weisbjerg, M. Brask, L. Alstrup, M. Johansen, L. Hymøller, M. K. Larsen, and P. Lund. 2016. Prediction of the methane conversion factor (Y_m) for dairy cows on the basis of national farm data. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 56:535–540. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN15520>.
- Honan, M., X. Feng, J. M. Tricarico, and E. Kebreab. 2022. Feed additives as a strategic approach to reduce enteric methane production in cattle: Modes of action, effectiveness and safety. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 62:1303–1317. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN20295>.
- Hörtenhuber, S. J., V. Größbacher, L. Schanz, and W. J. Zollitsch. 2023. Implementing IPCC 2019 Guidelines into a national inventory: Impacts of key changes in Austrian cattle and pig farming. *Sustainability (Basel)* 15:4814. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15064814>.
- Hristov, A. N., A. Bannink, M. Battelli, A. Belanche, M. C. Cajarville Sanz, G. Fernandez-Turren, F. Garcia, A. Jonker, D. A. Kenny, V. Lind, S. J. Meale, D. Meo Zilio, C. Muñoz, D. Pacheco, N. Peiren, M. Ramin, L. Rapetti, A. Schwarm, S. Stergiadis, K. Theodoridou,

- E. M. Ungerfeld, S. van Gastelen, D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz, S. M. Waters, and P. Lund. 2025. Feed additives for methane mitigation: Recommendations for testing enteric methane-mitigating feed additives in ruminant studies. *J. Dairy Sci.* 108:322–355. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25050>.
- Hristov, A. N., E. Kebreab, M. Niu, J. Oh, A. Bannink, A. R. Bayat, T. M. Boland, A. F. Brito, D. P. Casper, L. A. Crompton, J. Dijkstra, M. Eugene, P. C. Garnsworthy, N. Haque, A. L. F. Hellwing, P. Huhtanen, M. Kreuzer, B. Kuhla, P. Lund, J. Madsen, C. Martin, P. J. Moate, S. Muetzel, C. Munoz, N. Peiren, J. M. Powell, C. K. Reynolds, A. Schwarm, K. J. Shingfield, T. M. Storlien, M. R. Weisbjerg, D. R. Yanez-Ruiz, and Z. Yu. 2018. *Symposium review: Uncertainties in enteric methane inventories, measurement techniques, and prediction models.* *J. Dairy Sci.* 101:6655–6674. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-13536>.
- Huhtanen, P., E. H. Cabezas-Garcia, S. Utsumi, and S. Zimmerman. 2015. Comparison of methods to determine methane emissions from dairy cows in farm conditions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98:3394–3409. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-9118>.
- Ibidhi, R., T.-H. Kim, R. Bharanidharan, H.-J. Lee, Y.-K. Lee, N.-Y. Kim, and K.-H. Kim. 2021. Developing country-specific methane emission factors and carbon fluxes from enteric fermentation in South Korean dairy cattle production. *Sustainability (Basel)* 13:9133. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169133>.
- IPCC. 2006. 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Prepared by the National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme. H. S. Eggleston, L. Buendia, K. Miwa, T. Ngara, and K. Tanabe, ed. IGES, Japan. Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_10_Ch10_Livestock.pdf.
- IPCC. 2019. Chapter 10: Emissions from livestock and manure management. Pages 10.1–10.207 in 2019 Refinement to the 2006 guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use. E. Calvo Buendia, K. Tanabe, A. Kranjc, J. Baasansuren, M. Fukuda, S. Ngarize, A. Osako, Y. Pyroshenko, P. Shermanau, and S. Federici, ed. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland. Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/pdf/4_Volume4/19R_V4_Ch10_Livestock.pdf.
- IPCC. 2022. Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. P. R. Shukla, J. Skea, R. Slade, A. Al Khourdajie, R. van Diemen, D. McCollum, M. Pathak, S. Some, P. Vyas, R. Fradera, M. Belkacemi, A. Hasija, G. Lisboa, S. Luz, and J. Malley, ed. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Kebreab, E., A. Bannink, E. M. Pressman, N. Walker, A. Karagiannis, S. van Gastelen, and J. Dijkstra. 2023. A meta-analysis of effects of 3-nitrooxypropanol on methane production, yield, and intensity in dairy cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 106:927–936. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22211>.
- Kebreab, E., L. Tedeschi, J. Dijkstra, J. L. Ellis, A. Bannink, and J. France. 2016. Modeling greenhouse gas emissions from enteric fermentation. Pages 173–195 in *Synthesis and Modeling of Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Carbon Storage in Agricultural and Forest Systems to Guide Mitigation and Adaptation.* American Society of Agronomy, Crop Science Society of America, and Soil Science Society of America.
- Klop, G., J. Dijkstra, K. Dieho, W. H. Hendriks, and A. Bannink. 2017. Enteric methane production in lactating dairy cows with continuous feeding of essential oils or rotational feeding of essential oils and lauric acid. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100:3563–3575. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2016-12033>.
- Kouazounde, J. B., J. D. Gbenou, S. Babatounde, N. Srivastava, S. H. Eggleston, C. Antwi, J. Baah, and T. A. McAllister. 2015. Development of methane emission factors for enteric fermentation in cattle from Benin using IPCC Tier 2 methodology. *Animal* 9:526–533. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731114002626>.
- Lassey, K. R. 2007. Livestock methane emission: From the individual grazing animal through national inventories to the global methane cycle. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 142:120–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2006.03.028>.
- Latham, E. A., R. C. Anderson, W. E. Pinchak, and D. J. Nisbet. 2016. Insights on alterations to the rumen ecosystem by nitrate and nitro-compounds. *Front. Microbiol.* 7:228. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.00228>.
- Maigaard, M., M. R. Weisbjerg, M. Johansen, N. Walker, C. Ohlsson, and P. Lund. 2024. Effects of dietary fat, nitrate, and 3-nitrooxypropanol and their combinations on methane emission, feed intake, and milk production in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107:220–241. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2023-23420>.
- MAPA. 2024. Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación. Bases zootécnicas para el cálculo del balance alimentario de nitrógeno y de fósforo en porcino blanco. 2ª Edición (in Spanish). Accessed Oct. 29, 2024. https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/ganaderia/temas/ganaderia-y-medio-ambiente/porcino_blanco_2024_21-3-24subidoaweb_tcm30-440945.pdf.
- Muizelaar, W., M. Groot, G. van Duinkerken, R. Peters, and J. Dijkstra. 2021. Safety and transfer study: Transfer of bromoform present in *Asparagopsis taxiformis* to milk and urine of lactating dairy cows. *Foods* 10:584. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10030584>.
- Ndung'u, P. W., C. J. L. du Toit, T. Takahashi, M. Robertson-Dean, K. Butterbach-Bahl, L. Merbold, and J. P. Goopy. 2023. A simplified approach for producing Tier 2 enteric-methane emission factors based on East African smallholder farm data. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 63:227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN22082>.
- Nichols, K., A. Bannink, S. Pacheco, H. J. van Valenberg, J. Dijkstra, and H. van Laar. 2018. Feed and nitrogen efficiency are affected differently but milk lactose production is stimulated equally when isoenergetic protein and fat is supplemented in lactating dairy cow diets. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101:7857–7870. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-14276>.
- Nilsson, J., and M. Martin. 2022. Exploratory environmental assessment of large-scale cultivation of seaweed used to reduce enteric methane emissions. *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 30:413–423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.006>.
- Niu, M., E. Kebreab, A. N. Hristov, J. Oh, C. Arndt, A. Bannink, A. R. Bayat, A. F. Brito, T. Boland, D. Casper, L. A. Crompton, J. Dijkstra, M. A. Eugene, P. C. Garnsworthy, M. N. Haque, A. L. F. Hellwing, P. Huhtanen, M. Kreuzer, B. Kuhla, P. Lund, J. Madsen, C. Martin, S. C. McClelland, M. McGee, P. J. Moate, S. Muetzel, C. Munoz, P. O'Kiely, N. Peiren, C. K. Reynolds, A. Schwarm, K. J. Shingfield, T. M. Storlien, M. R. Weisbjerg, D. R. Yanez-Ruiz, and Z. Yu. 2018. Prediction of enteric methane production, yield, and intensity in dairy cattle using an intercontinental database. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 24:3368–3389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14094>.
- Oenema, O., H. Kros, and W. de Vries. 2003. Approaches and uncertainties in nutrient budgets: Implications for nutrient management and environmental policies. *Eur. J. Agron.* 20:3–16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301\(03\)00067-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(03)00067-4).
- Olijhoek, D. W., A. L. F. Hellwing, M. Brask, M. R. Weisbjerg, O. Hojberg, M. K. Larsen, J. Dijkstra, E. J. Erlandsen, and P. Lund. 2016. Effect of dietary nitrate level on enteric methane production, hydrogen emission, rumen fermentation, and nutrient digestibility in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 99:6191–6205. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10691>.
- Ouatohar, L., A. Bannink, G. Lanigan, and B. Amon. 2021. Modelling the effect of feeding management on greenhouse gas and nitrogen emissions in cattle farming systems. *Sci. Total Environ.* 776:145932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145932>.
- Owens, J. L., B. W. Thomas, J. L. Stoeckli, K. A. Beauchemin, T. A. McAllister, F. J. Larney, and X. Hao. 2020. Greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions from stored manure from beef cattle supplemented 3-nitrooxypropanol and monensin to reduce enteric methane emissions. *Sci. Rep.* 10:19310. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-75236-w>.
- Petersen, S. O., M. Blanchard, D. Chadwick, A. Del Prado, N. Edouard, J. Mosquera, and S. G. Sommer. 2013. Manure management for greenhouse gas mitigation. *Animal* 7:266–282. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731113000736>.
- Pressman, E. M., S. Liu, and F. M. Mitloehner. 2023. Methane emissions from California dairies estimated using novel climate metric Global

- Warming Potential Star show improved agreement with modeled warming dynamics. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 6:1072805. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.1072805>.
- Reynolds, C. K., D. J. Humphries, P. Kirton, M. Kindermann, S. Duval, and W. Steinberg. 2014. Effects of 3-nitrooxypropanol on methane emission, digestion, and energy and nitrogen balance of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97:3777–3789. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2013-7397>.
- Ridoutt, B. 2021. Climate neutral livestock production—A radiative forcing-based climate footprint approach. *J. Clean. Prod.* 291:125260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125260>.
- Ridoutt, B., S. A. Lehnert, S. Denman, E. Charmley, R. Kinley, and S. Dominik. 2022. Potential GHG emission benefits of *Asparagopsis taxiformis* feed supplement in Australian beef cattle feedlots. *J. Clean. Prod.* 337:130499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130499>.
- Romero-Perez, A., E. K. Okine, S. M. McGinn, L. L. Guan, M. Oba, S. M. Duval, M. Kindermann, and K. A. Beauchemin. 2014. The potential of 3-nitrooxypropanol to lower enteric methane emissions from beef cattle. *J. Anim. Sci.* 92:4682–4693. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2014-7573>.
- Schaubroeck, T. 2023. Relevance of attributional and consequential life cycle assessment for society and decision support. *Front. Sustain.* 4:1063583. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2023.1063583>.
- Schils, R. L. M., J. L. Ellis, C. A. M. de Klein, J. P. Lesschen, S. O. Petersen, and S. G. Sommer. 2012. Mitigation of greenhouse gases from agriculture: Role of models. *Acta Agric. Scand. A Anim. Sci.* 62:212–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2013.788205>.
- Schils, R. L. M., J. E. Olesen, A. del Prado, and J. F. Soussana. 2007. A review of farm level modelling approaches for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions from ruminant livestock systems. *Livest. Sci.* 112:240–251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2007.09.005>.
- Tedeschi, L. O., A. L. Abdalla, C. Alvarez, S. W. Anuga, J. Arango, K. A. Beauchemin, P. Becquet, A. Berndt, R. Burns, C. De Camillis, J. Chara, J. M. Echazarreta, M. Hassouna, D. Kenny, M. Mathot, R. M. Mauricio, S. C. McClelland, M. Niu, A. A. Onyango, R. Parajuli, L. G. R. Pereira, A. Del Prado, M. Paz Tieri, A. Uwizeye, and E. Kebreab. 2022. Quantification of methane emitted by ruminants: A review of methods. *J. Anim. Sci.* 100:skac197. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skac197>.
- Tricarico, J. M., F. Garcia, A. Bannink, S.-S. Lee, M. A. Miguel, J. R. Newbold, P. K. Rosenstien, M. R. Van der Saag, and D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz. 2025. Feed additives for methane mitigation: Regulatory frameworks and scientific evidence requirements for the authorization of feed additives to mitigate ruminant methane emissions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 108:395–410. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2024-25051>.
- Uddin, M. E., J. M. Tricarico, and E. Kebreab. 2022. Impact of nitrate and 3-nitrooxypropanol on the carbon footprints of milk from cattle produced in confined-feeding systems across regions in the United States: A life cycle analysis. *J. Dairy Sci.* 105:5074–5083. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2021-20988>.
- van Gastelen, S., E. E. A. Burgers, J. Dijkstra, R. de Mol, W. Muizelaar, N. Walker, and A. Bannink. 2024. Long-term effects of 3-nitrooxypropanol on methane emission and milk production characteristics in Holstein Friesian dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107:5556–5573. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2023-24198>.
- van Gastelen, S., D. Yanez-Ruiz, H. Khelil-Arfa, A. Blanchard, and A. Bannink. 2024. Effect of a blend of cinnamaldehyde, eugenol, and capsicum oleoresin on methane emission and lactation performance of Holstein-Friesian dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107:857–869. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2023-23406>.
- van Lingen, H. J., M. Niu, E. Kebreab, S. C. Valadares Filho, J. A. Rooke, C.-A. Duthie, A. Schwarm, M. Kreuzer, P. I. Hynd, M. Caetano, M. Eugène, C. Martin, M. McGee, P. O’Kiely, M. Hünerberg, T. A. McAllister, T. T. Berchielli, J. D. Messana, N. Peiren, A. V. Chaves, E. Charmley, N. A. Cole, K. E. Hales, S.-S. Lee, A. Berndt, C. K. Reynolds, L. A. Crompton, A.-R. Bayat, D. R. Yáñez-Ruiz, Z. Yu, A. Bannink, J. Dijkstra, D. P. Casper, and A. N. Hristov. 2019. Prediction of enteric methane production, yield and intensity of beef cattle using an intercontinental database. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 283:106575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106575>.
- van Zijderveld, S. M., W. J. Gerrits, J. A. Apajalahti, J. R. Newbold, J. Dijkstra, R. A. Leng, and H. B. Perdok. 2010. Nitrate and sulfate: Effective alternative hydrogen sinks for mitigation of ruminal methane production in sheep. *J. Dairy Sci.* 93:5856–5866. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3281>.
- VERRA. 2021. Verified Carbon Standard (VCS). Accessed Oct. 20, 2024. <https://verra.org/programs/verified-carbon-standard/>.
- Vibart, R., C. de Klein, A. Jonker, T. van der Weerden, A. Bannink, A. R. Bayat, L. Crompton, A. Durand, M. Eugene, K. Klumpp, B. Kuhla, G. Lanigan, P. Lund, M. Ramin, and F. Salazar. 2021. Challenges and opportunities to capture dietary effects in on-farm greenhouse gas emissions models of ruminant systems. *Sci. Total Environ.* 769:144989. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.144989>.

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